

New Water Culture Questionnaire - Melilla

INSTRUCTIONS:

Please note that this questionnaire is completely anonymous. We are interested in questions related to the use, management and saving of water. Please mark with an X the degree of agreement with the following statements. There are no right or wrong answers.

AGE: __ **GENDER:** Male Female Prefer not to say **LOCATION WHERE YOU TEACH:** _____

AGE OF THE STUDENTS YOU TEACH: _____ **NATURAL SCIENCES** **SOCIAL SCIENCES**

QUESTION	ESCALE			
	Totally disagree	Disagree	Agree	Totally agree
1. The fresh water on Earth is insufficient				
2. Water scarcity is due to water imbalance				
3. Freshwater is not scarce. There is enough for the Earth's inhabitants				
4. Water scarcity lies in the quality of available water due to pollution and degradation of the natural environment				
5. Reservoirs, desalination plants, dams...enable us to get more water				
6. There are desertified areas that require the transfer of water from more water-rich areas				
7. In desertified areas, it is necessary to implement technologies and economic activities adapted to the available water				
8. The main problems affecting water in Spain are:	a. Scarcity			
	b. Poor management of water supplied			
	c. Dumping of waste waters without treatment			
	d. Poor water quality			
	e. Environmental degradation			
9. The main problems affecting water in Melilla are:	a. Scarcity			
	b. Poor management of water supplied			
	c. Dumping of waste waters without treatment			
	d. Poor water quality			
	e. Environmental degradation			
10. The water problem should be solved by	a. Central Government			
	b. Local Government			
	c. The citizens			
11. Industrial facilities used to obtain more water damage the environment				
12. With climate change, water resources will become increasingly scarce				
13. When I am in locations without water problems, I don't mind wasting water because it won't affect the environment				
14. The following solutions that are	a. Water transfers			
	b. Dam building			

QUESTION		ESCALE			
		Totally disagree	Disagree	Agree	Totally agree
often used to get the water we consume are harmful to the environment:	c. Reservoir construction				
	d. Desalination plants				
	e. Construction of independent rainwater collection systems				
15. If you were a water manager in Spain, you would opt for:	a. More reservoirs to ensure supply				
	b. Water transfers to ensure supply				
	c. Controlling water demand and applying stringent costs to those that consume the most				
	d. Raising citizen awareness to reduce personal, family and professional consumption				
	e. Reducing leakage in the water networks				
	f. Reusing treated water				
16. If you were responsible for water management in Melilla, you would opt for:	a. Building another desalination plant				
	b. Encouraging water saving				
	c. Extracting more water from wells				
	d. Building more reservoirs				
	e. Reducing leakage in the water networks				
	f. Reusing treated water				
17. The water I use at home comes from:	a. Wells				
	b. The sea				
	c. Directly from rain				
18. The water we have used goes to:	a. Directly to the sea				
	b. Directly to the river				
	c. Irrigation water, after treatment				
	d. As drinking water, after treatment				
19. Water is treated before reaching my home					
20. The water that comes from my home must receive treatment					
21. Water consumption in Melilla is much higher than the national average					
22. Given the amount of water on Earth, I don't think it is important to save water					
23. In Spain we must save water					
24. In Melilla we must save water					
25. We could save water in homes by:	a. Turning off the tap when brushing my teeth or soaping				
	b. Using a dishwasher				
	c. Consuming foods of mainly vegetable origin				
	d. Reusing shower water for the toilet				
	e. Buying fewer clothes				
	f. Consuming less meat				

QUESTION		ESCALE			
		Totally disagree	Disagree	Agree	Totally agree
26. In our urban environment we could save water by:	a. Adapting crop types to water availability				
	b. Adapting ornamental plants to water availability				
	c. Building independent rainwater collection systems				
	d. Increasing the production of necessary products instead of importing them				
	e. Doing away with golf courses				
	f. Eliminating private swimming pools				
27. The following actions affect water availability:	a. Buying a lot of clothing				
	b. Frequently changing smartphone, Tablet, computer...				
	c. Using plastic bags				
	d. Cutting down many trees				